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DECOLONIZING METHODOLOGY: PROPOSING *KACHAHARĪ* AS SOCIO-CULTURALLY ACCEPTABLE QUALITATIVE METHOD

Abstract: In this article, I propose *Kachaharī* as an anthropologically useful and socio-culturally acceptable data collection method, which is similar to focus group discussions, yet differs in a particular way: the participants, not the researcher, drive the discussion. This cultural practice prevails in South Asia with some differences and similarities in terms of names and proceedings, particularly in Pakistan's Sindh province. This article thoroughly elucidates *Kachahārī* through ascertaining its socio-cultural history, composition, effectiveness, the special circumstances in which it occurs, and how it is similar to yet differs from the focus group discussion. My aim is not to invent a method but to highlight one that already exists in certain socio-cultural settings and can be used as a qualitative method for social science research. I discovered it during my PhD fieldwork in Sindh Province, Pakistan in 2014. Given that this method was already in use in that cultural setting, I found it easy to adapt for rapid and culturally appropriate data collection. I show that the role of the researcher in the success of this method is key, as the group conversation may easily drift off-topic and it is the researcher's task to bring the conversation back to the topic at hand. This must be done in a subtle and indirect way that does not involve taking direct charge of the discussion. The researcher must also be both an attentive participant and a keen listener. I present and describe this method herein, as *Kachaharī* might also be helpful for other researchers in other socio-cultural settings.

Keywords: methodology; qualitative; Kahchari; Group discussion; Focus group discussion; South Asia

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Introduction

How to obtain data that is as authentic as possible? This question has kept ethnographic fieldwork at the center of anthropology (Gupta and Ferguson 1997). This article addresses this question from the South Asian context, with particular focus on Pakistan's Sindh Province. In this article, I propose *Kachaharī* as an anthropologically useful and socio-culturally acceptable data collection method, which is similar to focus group discussions, yet differs in that the participants, not the researcher, drive the discussion.

Kachahār is a local word that means discussions; ethnographically it “is an adaptation of the “focus group” discussion, with the difference that the discussion is driven not by a researcher but by participants; it builds on an existing culturally recognized local social process for discussing and solving a particular problem” (Ali, Sadique, and Ali 2021). This cultural practice prevails in South Asia with some differences and similarities in terms of names and proceedings, particularly in Pakistan's Sindh province, where I discovered this method and employed it to great advantage.

Herein, I thoroughly elucidate *Kachahārī* via describing its socio-cultural history, composition, effectiveness, and the circumstances in which it occurs. My aim is not to invent a method but to highlight one that already exists in certain socio-cultural settings and can be used as a qualitative method for social science research. I trust that social scientists, in particular anthropologists with a geographical focus on South Asia, will find the research method presented in this article both helpful and thought-provoking. Inviting further debates and discussions, I seek to add something new to the anthropological data collection toolkit, particularly for this region. To date, I have read or seen no article on the *Kachaharī*; thus I consider it important for me to present it here, as this method can “help us better understand how ordinary people in some locality make sense of the world they live in and how we can compare their ideas, practices, and experiences with those of others” (Berger 2012, 326).

I discovered this locally existing method during my PhD fieldwork on *Constructing and Negotiating Measles: The Case of Sindh Province of Pakistan* (Ali 2020). I entered the field equipped with the usual anthropological toolkit, consisting of qualitative and quantitative methods: participant observation; interviews; interview guides; focus group and informal group discussions; socio-economic and census survey forms; photography; recording devices; and a notebook for fieldnote-jotting.

The informal group discussions that I participated in led me to the discovery of *Kachaharī*. Although other anthropologists have also conducted fieldwork in Sindh Province, none have discussed *Kachaharī*.

History: The sociocultural roots of *Kahchārī*

On this method, there is no written record available. Yet according to one of my interlocutors for my PhD research, its oral history dates to the origin of the “Sindhi” culture. When did this Sindhi culture emerge? This is a challenging question, as the history of Sindh is linked with the Indus Valley Civilization, one of the world’s most ancient civilizations, which flourished along the Indus River from 3300–1300 BCE, yet has roots in earlier predecessor cultures starting around 7500 BCE. The remains of *Moen-jo-Daro* (Mound of the Dead)—an ancient city of the Indus Valley civilization; *Kotdiji*—considered to be the forerunner of the Indus Civilization, it was occupied as early as 3300 BCE; and *Aamri*--an ancient settlement in modern-day Sindh that dates back to 3600 BCE--are considered to be evidence of this long history. Sindh was one of the earliest regions to be conquered by the Arabs and influenced by Islam after 720 CE. Before this period, it was heavily Hindu and Buddhist.

In today’s Sindh Province, as I will demonstrate, this likely ancient means of discussion is still in use. The men of these geographical areas usually gather informally and voluntarily, especially in the evening, at a place called *Otaq* or *Baithak* (a guest house for male members) to share and discuss the routine proceedings of their lives--personal, collective, socio-economic, political, religious, news, jokes, stories (*Nazir*), past stories (of themselves, of their parents, of someone else, or the ruler of the area, of their achievement, distinctions, cattle, oxen) and so on. The discussion would begin on any topic and proceed from there.

Moreover, this gathering also takes place as soon as a guest arrives at anyone’s *Otaq*. News spreads in the village; in some cases, the host also sends a message through a child (especially a male) to some prestigious individuals of the village. The level of prestige such a message carries may be determined by the communication skills, economic situation, education, and social position of the sender of that message or of his guest. In some cases, male members of the village voluntarily join the gathering after hearing the news about a guest’s arrival. In the former situation (when a guest arrives), the host welcomes the prestigious person with these words, “We were missing your presence. Our gathering was incomplete without you. Therefore, we sent the messenger for you.” In the latter case, the prestigious person (the host) begins the conversation by saying, “As soon as the news reached my ears, I felt the responsibility to arrive without taking care of my business and formalities to be part of this great *Kachaharī* or *Mehfil*” (gathering).

In a guest’s case, a gathering commences formally when an older person from the host’s family seeks permission from every participant while specifically asking the most prestigious ones, “*Ada, ijazat aahy, ady khan hawal wathun?*” [my translation: “Brother, would you like to give me permission to inquire about the purpose of our guest’s visit?”]. In response, participants will say, “*Ji, ada,*

Bismillah” [“Yes, brother, in the name of God”]. Next, the host would inquire about the visit’s purpose by, “*Ji ada, day hal awhal*” [“Yes, brother, please let us know is everything all right?”]. Then the guest explains whether he has come only to visit or has a specific purpose—that purpose may be monetary, bringing a marriage proposal or an invitation to a marriage, news of someone’s death or critical illness, a quarrel in his village, and so forth. Further proceedings continue accordingly. A *Kachaharī* can also be arranged to discuss a particular issue that has come up in that village or area.

I discovered this method while being treated as a guest. I was born and raised in Sindh Province, so I knew that upon my arrival in the two villages in rural Sindh that I had selected for my Ph.D. research, I should immediately seek out the *Otaq*, as that was where I was most likely to meet people who could help me with my research. There it became possible to meet the heads of the villages, who asked me who I am, why I was there, and what they could do for me. This was my entry into the field. They welcomed me and offered me all the support they could provide. In one village, the *Otaq* (men’s house) is called a *Waddera*, and in other, a *Patel*. The English translation or equivalent of both these terms is the ‘head’ or the ‘influential’. My arrival triggered an informal *Kachaharī*. The men offered me tea, followed by lunch, so I quickly learned that the serving of food is an integral part of *Kachaharī*.

Food as a crucial feature of *Kachaharī*

The type and quantity of food served during a *Kachaharī* depend on its level of formality. If it is informal—just among the male villagers—it can include what is already cooked for the family or mostly cooked for the guests. For instance, if *Kachaharī* is between villagers, what has been prepared for the family, may be served at *Otaq*. It is also important to mention that the food may not be sent for every participant, but the family member. Yet, the black tea with milk is prepared for every participant, in this case.

In contrast, if a guest arrives and a more formal *Kachaharī* is held, exceptional food is cooked, which may include fish, or curry made from local chickens, Saag (green leaves), white rice, chapatti, and biryani (rice with chicken). This meal will be served to every participant in the *Kachaharī*.

The Timing of *Kachaharī*

Kachaharī takes place almost daily in the evenings. There is a gender difference. Male village members most often meet at the *Otaq*. It generally continues until 20:00–21:00 hours; in the case of a guest, it often reaches

midnight. In small cities, it may also occur at a tea stall, as during these gatherings, tea plays a significant role. The timing of *Kachaharī* at a tea stall starts approximately at 10:00 and ends at 17:00. The older generation asserts that some three-four decades ago, tea was not a part of food patterns; rather, it was introduced by the English. One 80-year-old male interlocutor stated, “The Englishmen used to take tea to be active whenever they felt tired, while we people are taking in an excessive amount without any [physical] need.” Presently, tea is a compulsory part of the gatherings.

In contrast, female village members sit and talk in their houses about some special events such as marriage, death, inquiring about someone’s health, and visiting relatives. The marriage and death ceremonies are considered special events, in which almost all relatives and friends participate and share their life experiences. In some cases, women and men sit in groups and talk together.

The famous *Matchà* *Kachaharī* occurs during the winter season. It is similar to bonfire (an open fire during winter). Also, during the peak season of summer, when the temperature increases from 40 degrees Celsius to 50 plus degrees, and it becomes too hard to perform any physical work, men and women also gather in the afternoons. During these gatherings, they may play local games, including card games, and work on puzzles such as *16 tinn*, *9 tinn*, *sheenh bakari*, playing cards, and give *ggujharat* (puzzles). These games help pass the time, provide a great source of entertainment, and enhance people’s intelligence and analytical skills. Sometimes, they create voluntary teams that play in tournaments. In the case of a guest, the host tries to give him a strong partner to make sure that he will win.

Why Use *Kachaharī* as a Research Method?

Advantages

The multiple advantages of *Kachaharī* as a research method lie in its socio-cultural roots. These advantages include:

- (1) It helps greatly to begin the research project with the formal local introduction of the researcher and the project, and by receiving formal social permission to carry it out.
- (2) It shortens the phase of building rapport, as the needed rapport is quickly built during the *Kachaharī*.
- (3) It provides the researcher with social recognition, as the most prestigious or influential man of the village introduces the researcher and welcomes him warmly. *Kachaharī* will work for female researchers as well.
- (4) It is qualitative and provides comprehensive and detailed data.

- (5) It can help to cross-check the data obtained through other tools and techniques.
- (6) Attending several *Kachaharion* (plural) would provide the researcher with multiple opportunities to learn about the accepted codes of conduct, of that village and the primary concerns of daily life.
- (7) The knowledge and understandings gained during a *Kachaharī* can help the researcher to develop, change, add to, and complement other methods of data collection.
- (8) The local participants, not the researcher have the control (DeWalt and DeWalt 2011, 137–156) on various types of interviews.
- (9) *Kachaharī* gives the researcher the advantage of carrying out a long conversation without making the participants exhausted or annoyed (ibid). Participation in a *Kachaharī* can be fun, as the participants are at ease and may share jokes and funny stories, or simply talk about whatever they please. The choice is theirs, without any imposition, enforcement, or pressure driven by the researcher.

Disadvantages

One of the significant disadvantages of *Kachaharī* is the difficulty of getting participants to stay on topic, especially if one lacks proficiency in the local language. The researcher may call for a *Kachaharī* to address a particular topic, or try to gently guide an existing *Kachaharī* toward a specific topic, only to find that it is like “herding cats”: participants often drift off topic, and since the researcher is not in control, it can be very hard to get them to come back to the topic the researcher wants them to address. It also requires a great deal of close attention to listen to and memorize the relevant data due to its length and quantity (DeWalt and DeWalt 2011, 155–56); since a *Kachaharī* is usually informal in nature, it would not look appropriate for the researcher to be constantly taking notes. Yet it is possible to record these discussions; the downside of course is the countless hours it takes to transcribe and translate these recordings, which are often difficult to understand when several people are talking at once or are speaking in very low voices.

Another potential disadvantage is that, if the researcher is not vigilant enough, then an influential host might manipulate him or dominate the conversation, thereby silencing others who might wish to share their views. And exclusive reliance on this method may also exclude specific individuals who, for some social reasons, such as disputes, do not visit that *Otaq*, resulting in the researcher not leaning the perspectives of the community as a whole. This is why *Kachaharī* works best when supplemented with other research methodologies such as one-on-one interviews.

Similarities and differences between *Kachaharī* and Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

How is Kachaharī similar to FGD?

Both of these research methods involve a group of people sitting and discussing a topic or topics in which the researcher is interested. *Kachaharī* has characteristics similar to those that DeWalt and DeWalt (2011, 137–38) identify for an FGD: “the researcher is interested in some phenomena more than others” and therefore is likely to intentionally direct the conversation and to ask many questions that are unlikely to be raised “in a casual conversation among acquaintances.”

How is Kachaharī different from an FGD?

The focus group emerged as a sociological method to research advertising and marketing (Merton and Kendall 1946), along with the focused interview (Merton 1987). The acceptable definition of the focus group is “a carefully planned discussion designed to obtain perceptions on a defined area of interest in a permissive, nonthreatening environment” (Krueger and Casey 2014, 2). In contrast, *Kachaharī* is neither a controlled nor a researcher-generated gathering. However, a researcher might request to arrange one. It occurs naturally in those settings where it is common. The researcher sits at an *Otaq*, and the people come to join, which is a usual practice for them. Or they are already present, and the researcher joins them. In either case, the researcher is not the driver but a participant.

Why Kachaharī, but not FGD?

Again, I did not choose this method before going into the field; rather, I discovered it after I arrived. Once I realized its value, I used it for the following reasons: (1) It already had space, recognition, acceptance, and understanding in that specific socio-cultural setting; (2) It is not a researcher-driven method but rather a participant-driven method; the researcher is a participant who subtly tries to guide the discussion his way, and often fails and has to try again; (3) Since it is socio-culturally rooted, it helps the researcher obtain the required data without distorting the existing social conditions;. (4) It plays a pivotal role in the researchers’ acceptance by the locals; (5) Participants do not feel any pressure to answer; they just tell or share whatever they want; (6) *Kachaharī* provides an emic perspective that keeps the researcher from trying to fit what he or she learns into etic categories that may not reflect actual local perspectives.

Conclusion

In this article, I have presented a new/old research method called *Kachaharī*, which I discovered upon my entry into the field in two rural villages in Sindh Province, Pakistan. I have described this method, explained its similarities to and differences from the focus group discussion, and detailed its advantages and disadvantages. This novel discovery may lead to further discoveries of more culturally appropriate and sensitive research methods that foreground the people, not the researcher.

As Berger (2012, 325) notes, “In a next step, a certain perspective or a generalization of a specific phenomenon is transferred to other regions or other parts of the globe: Trobriand reciprocity is compared to gift-giving in India or African lineage theory is tested in highland Papua New Guinea. Such direct transplantations of theoretical perspectives do not always work, but such a comparative perspective [can help to] refine our conceptual tools in close dialogue with ethnographic data.” Thus it is my hope that this method will be of use to others who are conducting research in relevant sociocultural contexts.

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